

Gas Loop

Why should it be done?

- Reduction of ammonia by 54%
- Limiting ammonia emissions reduces both acidification by 21% and the formation of particulates by 17%
- The efficiency in ammonia removals in the air flow between in and out was on average 86% during the year.
- Improving of indoor air quality, reducing ammonia in the treated room by 62% on average.
- Improvement in animal welfare and working conditions for staff.
- Production of an ammonium sulphate solution in line with EU Regulation 2019/1009 for the category N-based liquid inorganic fertilisers (category PFC1(C)(I)(b)(i)).
- The recovery of this fertiliser solution allows to avoid the share of GHG due to the synthesis of industrial nitrogenous.

Further details

- € **Total budget** € 189.757,14
- Total financed** € 176.081,45
- Main funding source:** Rural development 2014-2020 for Operational Groups
- Rural Development Programme:** 2014IT06RDRP003 Italy - Rural Development Programme (Regional) - Emilia-Romagna
- 🕒 **Ended, 2021-2023**
- 📍 **Emilia-Romagna, Italy**
- 👤 **Centro Ricerche Produzioni Animali**
Project coordinator - Research institute - Reggio Emilia (Italy)
info@crpa.it

Economic case study of ammonia air treatment in pig livestock for nitrogen recovery

Objectives

The objective of this OG is to generate a nitrogen virtuous cycle (loop) in pig farming. By capturing ammonia emissions and producing ammonium sulphate, it reduces chemical inputs for farming crops and consequently GHG emissions generated by their industrial production. Furthermore, improving the air quality inside the pig barn, it aims to enhancing animal welfare.

Economic assessment

An assessment of economic feasibility of the ammonia air treatment system innovation has been carried out based on a case study. The costs of a complete installation or building arrangement for afterwards installation of the ammonia air treatment system have been estimated. Moreover, has been assessed the impact on the value of kg meat produced (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Cost items and their percentage impact on the annual management costs (productive costs increment equal to 0.16 cents per kg meat)

Costs rate of kg meat produced

The treatment system involves cost between 0,15 and 0,17 €/kg of live weight sold, namely an **impact of 7.3% on the sales value** which is related to the quotation of 2.27 €/kg chain for heavy pigs in the protected circuit for the PDO (CUN pigs, December 2023).

Expences and profits are calculated according to the annuity.

Estimation costs

- Demolition 90,000 €
- Total construction 1,284,400 € (SAU animal available surface 1.16 m² /head - 892 €/place)
- Total ammonia air treatment system installation 208,000 €, of which 13.5% due to the arrangement works
- Installation of treatment air system is 16.2% of the base cost of the pig barn
- Suitable building arrangement 28,000 €, i.e. 2.2% of the base cost of the pig barn

Conclusion

Considering the modest cost of arrangement works compared to the total cost of construction of a pig barn, it is advisable to always provide for these works, because it will allow easy implementation the air treatment system afterwards.

Lastly, considering that the application of systems to reduce environmental impacts can lead to high costs, systems such as ammonia treatment air system should be economically supported.

Case study

Società Agricola Colombaro from Formigine (Modena) has been chosen as case study.

The livestock pig was an open-cycle fattening farm to produce heavy pigs (170 kg) intended for Parma ham PDO.

The case study included the demolition of one pig barn and the construction of a new one with the same dimension and capacity (114,96 x 18,6 m) for 1440 animal places and equipped by ammonia air treatment system.

Assume a S16 type of partially slotted floor that consider all likely future animal welfare regulations.

Pig barn of case study

- 2) Layout of the new pig barn
- 3) Intake ducts and positioning of the 4 treatments air systems
- 4) Cross-section of the new pig barn

NUTRI-KNOW

Learn more about the project at www.nutri-know.eu

Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Commission. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

